

Some Characteristics of Double Vertex Graph

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Abstract

The *double vertex graph* $U_2(G)$ of a graph G of order $n \geq 2$ is the graph whose vertex set consists of all $\binom{n}{2}$ unordered pairs of vertices of G and where two vertices $\{a, b\}$ and $\{c, d\}$ are adjacent if and only if $|\{a, b\} \cap \{c, d\}| = 1$ and if $a = c$, then b and d are adjacent in G . In this paper, we discuss some properties of $U_2(G)$ related to degree and distances. We also have obtained graphs G whose double vertex graphs contain G as a subgraph.

1. Introduction

All graphs G considered here are simple, finite and connected of order $n \geq 2$ and size m . Let $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ represent the vertex set and edge set of G , respectively. Chartrand introduced the term graph-valued function for any kind of rule or procedure which yields a unique graph from a given graph. In literature, there are many graph-valued functions studied, the earliest being line graph of a graph. The *double vertex graph* $U_2(G)$, is one such graph-valued function, introduced by Alavi.et.al[2].

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Figure 1: The graph G and its double vertex graph

For a graph G of order $n \geq 2$, $U_2(G)$ is the graph whose vertex set consists of all $\binom{n}{2}$ unordered pairs from $V(G)$ and where two vertices $\{a, b\}$ and $\{c, d\}$ are adjacent if and only if $|\{a, b\} \cap \{c, d\}| = 1$ and if $a = c$, then b and d are adjacent in G . The properties such as connectivity, planarity and traversability of double vertex graphs are well studied in [2,3,4].

In this paper, we characterize double vertex graphs that have pendant vertex, full degree vertex and isolated vertices. The double vertex graph that contains G as subgraph are investigated. Further, tight bounds for eccentricity of a vertex of $U_2(G)$ are obtained.

For undefined terminologies and notations refer to the text by G.Chartrand[1].

2. Preliminaries

A vertex $\{x, y\}$ of $U_2(G)$ is called a line pair or a non line pair according as x and y are adjacent or non adjacent in G . Then the vertex set of $U_2(G)$ can be partitioned into sets U and W where U is the set of line pairs and W the set of nonlinear pairs.

Theorem 2.1. $U_2(G)$ is connected if and only if G is connected.

Theorem 2.2. For any vertex $\{x, y\}$ of $U_2(G)$,

$$\deg\{x, y\} = \begin{cases} \deg x + \deg y - 2 & \text{if } xy \in E(G) \\ \deg x + \deg y & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3.Results

We begin with the following result:

Theorem 3.1. $U_2(G)$ is totally disconnected if and only if G is totally disconnected.

Proof: Suppose G is totally disconnected then every two vertices are non adjacent. Therefore every vertex in $U_2(G)$ is a non line pair and for a non line pair $\{x, y\}$ of $U_2(G)$, $deg\{x, y\} = 0$.

Conversely, if $U_2(G)$ is totally disconnected then G must be same as well since an edge e of G gives rise to $n - 2$ edges in $U_2(G)$. ■

Theorem 3.2. $U_2(G)$ has a full degree vertex if and only if $G \cong K_3, P_3$.

Proof: Suppose $U_2(G)$ has a full degree vertex. Then $U_2(G)$ is connected and by Theorem 2.1, G is connected. Let $n \geq 4$ and u, v, w, x be any four distinct vertices of G . Then the vertices $\{u, v\}$ and $\{w, x\}$ of $U_2(G)$ are non adjacent. Therefore, if G has four or more vertices then $U_2(G)$ has no full degree vertex.

However, if $n = 3$ the possible connected graphs are K_3 and P_3 and $U_2(K_3) \cong K_3, U_2(P_3) \cong P_3$. Both these graphs have full degree vertex.

If $n = 2, G \cong K_2$ is the only connected graph and $U_2(K_2) \cong K_1$.

Converse is obvious. ■

Lemma 3.3. If $H(\neq G)$ is any vertex induced subgraph of a graph G then for each $w \in V(G) - V(H)$ there corresponds a subgraph of $U_2(G)$ isomorphic to H .

Proof: Consider a vertex induced subgraph $H(\neq G)$ of G and for each $w \in V(G) - V(H)$, $H_w = \{\{v, w\} : v \in V(H)\}$ is a subset of $V(U_2(G))$. Define the function $\phi: V(H) \rightarrow V(H_w)$ given by $\phi(v) = \{v, w\}$. Clearly ϕ is a bijection and any two vertices $\{x, w\}$ and $\{y, w\}$ of H_w are adjacent in $U_2(G)$ if and only if x and y are adjacent in G (therefore in H). Thus $\langle H_w \rangle$ of $U_2(G)$ is isomorphic to H .

Figure 2: Illustration of Theorem 3.4

In particular, for a vertex $v \in V(G)$, the induced subgraph $G - v$ of G is isomorphic to $\langle H_v \rangle$ of $U_2(G)$. ■

Theorem 3.4. $U_2(G)$ has a subgraph isomorphic to G if one of the following condition holds:

- i) G has a vertex of degree two
- ii) G has a cut vertex incident with atleast two bridges one of which is a pendant edge

Proof: Let v be a vertex of degree two and vx and vy be the edges incident at v . Then by Lemma 3.3, $\langle H_v \rangle$ is isomorphic to $G - v$ and the vertex $\{x, y\}$ (not in H_v) is adjacent to both $\{v, x\}$ and $\{v, y\}$ of H_v and the subgraph induced by $H_v \cup \{x, y\}$ is isomorphic to G .

Now, assume G has no vertex of degree two. Let v be a cut vertex incident with bridges vx and vw where vw be a pendant edge. Deletion of vw and vx disconnects G giving rise to components, say, G_1 , G_2 and G_3 . Let G_1 be the component containing v , G_2 containing x and G_3 is a trivial component containing isolated vertex w . Now in $U_2(G)$ the subgraph G_{1x} induced by the vertices $\{x, v_i\}/v_i \in V(G_1)\}$ is isomorphic to G_1 and the subgraph G_{2w} induced by the vertices $\{w, x_i\}/x_i \in V(G_2)\}$ is isomorphic to G_2 in G . Further the vertices $\{v, x\} \in G_{1x}$ and $\{w, x\} \in G_{2w}$ are adjacent in $U_2(G)$ since vw is an edge in G . Therefore the subgraph $G_{1x} \cup G_{2w}$ of $U_2(G)$ is isomorphic to $G - w$. Since $degx \geq 3$ there exists atleast one vertex x_k adjacent to x in G such that vertex $\{v, x\}$ of $G_{1x} \cup G_{2w}$ is adjacent to the vertex $\{v, x_k\}$ in $U_2(G)$. Therefore the subgraph formed by $G_{1x} \cup G_{2w} \cup \{v, x_k\}$ is isomorphic to G . ■

Corollary 3.5. *If $G \cong C_n$ or P_n or $K_4 - e$ then $U_2(G)$ has exactly $n - 2$ edge disjoint subgraphs each isomorphic to G .*

Corollary 3.6. *For a path P_n , $U_2(P_n)$ has k vertex disjoint paths each isomorphic to P_n , $k = \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$.*

However, for $G \cong K_n, K_{1,n}$, $U_2(G)$ has no subgraph isomorphic to G . ■

Theorem 3.7. *$U_2(G)$ is claw free if and only if G has no*

- i) *induced subgraph isomorphic to C_4 or P_4 , or*
- ii) *subgraph isomorphic to $K_{1,2} \cup K_2$, or*
- iii) *proper subgraph isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$.*

Proof: We prove the equivalent statement that $U_2(G)$ has an induced subgraph H' isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$ if and only if G has an induced subgraph H isomorphic to C_4 or P_4 or a subgraph isomorphic to $K_{1,2} \cup K_2$ and a proper subgraph isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$.

For the claw H' , let $\{u, v\}$ be the central vertex. Then three cases arise due to nature of the end vertices of H' .

Case 1 Let $\{u, w\}, \{u, p\}, \{v, w\}$ be the end vertices of the claw H' . Then $\{u, w\}, \{u, p\}$ and $\{v, w\}$ induce a null graph in $U_2(G)$. So in G , v and w ; v and p ; u and w are adjacent whereas w and p ; u and v are not adjacent. However, u and p can be either adjacent or not adjacent. If u and p are non adjacent then the vertex set $\{u, w, v, p\}$ induce a P_4 in G on the other hand $\{u, w, v, p\}$ induce a subgraph $H \cong P_4$ in G on the other hand u, w, v, p induce a C_4 if u and p are adjacent.

Case 2 If $\{u, w\}, \{u, p\}, \{v, z\}$ are the end vertices of the claw H' then $\{u, w\}, \{u, p\}, \{v, z\}$ induce a null graph in $U_2(G)$. So in G , v and w ; v and p ; u and z are adjacent whereas w and p are non adjacent. Then the vertex set $\{v, w, p, u, z\}$ induces a $K_2 \cup K_{1,2}$ in G .

Figure 3: H' and H of Theorem 3.7

Case 3 If $\{u, w\}, \{u, p\}, \{u, r\}$ are the end vertices of the claw H' then $\{u, w\}, \{u, p\}, \{u, r\}$ induce a null graph in $U_2(G)$. So in G , v and w ; v and p ; v and r are adjacent whereas w and p ; p and r ; w and r are non adjacent. Then the vertex set $\{u, v, w, p, r\}$ induce a proper subgraph $K_{1,3}$ in G . Conversely, if G has an induced $C_4: x, y, z, w, x$. Then in $U_2(G)$ the subgraph induced by the vertices $\{w, z\}, \{y, z\}, \{x, y\}, \{x, z\}$ is isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$ with $\{x, z\}$ as central vertex.

Similarly, if G has an induced $P_4: x, y, z, w$ then in $U_2(G)$ the subgraph induced by the vertices $\{x, y\}, \{w, x\}, \{z, y\}, \{x, z\}$ is isomorphic to $K_{1,3}$ with $\{x, z\}$ as central vertex.

Further, if G has a subgraph $K_2 \cup K_{1,2}$ where u, w induces a K_2 and z, v, p induces a $K_{1,2}$. Then in $U_2(G)$, the vertices $\{u, z\}, \{u, v\}, \{u, p\}, \{w, v\}$ induce a claw with $\{u, v\}$ as central vertex. Lastly,

if G has a proper subgraph $K_{1,3}$ with u as central vertex and x, y, z as terminal vertices. Then there exists atleast one vertex $w \neq x, y, z, u$ in G so that $\{x, w\}, \{y, w\}, \{z, w\}, \{u, w\}$ form a claw in $U_2(G)$ with $\{u, w\}$ as central vertex.

Hence the theorem. ■

Theorem 3.8. *A vertex $\{x, y\}$ of $U_2(G)$ is a pendant vertex if and only if one of the two vertices x, y is a pendant vertex and other is either a vertex of degree two or an isolated vertex.*

Proof. Suppose the pendant vertex $\{x, y\}$ is a line pair in $U_2(G)$ then $deg\{x, y\} = degx + degy - 2 = 1$ which implies $degx + degy = 3$ that is one of the vertex is pendant and other is of degree two. If $\{x, y\}$ is a non line pair then $deg\{x, y\} = degx + degy = 1$ which implies one of the vertex is isolated and other one is pendant.

Conversly, if $degx = 1, degy = 2$ and x, y are adjacent in G then $deg\{x, y\} = 1 + 2 - 2 = 1$ and if $degx = 0, degy = 1$ then $deg\{x, y\} = 1$.

Hence the theorem. ■

3.References

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